

Aspects of The Pedagogical Experience of the Teacher of Physical Education and Sport

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the study of some aspects of pedagogical skill, pedagogical culture, the study of the level of managerial competence, the degree of professional "burnout" of physical culture and sports teachers. The study used a set of methodological tools (survey methods, questionnaires, observations, analysis. In conclusion, conclusions are drawn.

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The development of children and youth, student sports, the improvement of high-performance sports requires the involvement of qualified specialists, coaches, physical education teachers. In the concept of the state program for the development of physical culture and sports, based on the decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers on measures to develop physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan, such areas as: improving the organization and management of physical culture and sports, scientific research, methodological and medical support in the field of sports; improvement of personnel policy. Particular importance and attention in the formation of a comprehensively developed personality is given to the management personnel of children and youth schools, national teams, coaching staff, qualified teachers of physical education and sports. A sports professional must be able to make responsible and independent decisions. Competently organize professional activities with managerial competence.

In the research works of many authors, questions of pedagogical culture are studied.

Assessment of the activities of management personnel is given in the works of V.G. Avramenko, T.I. Bagaeva, (1990), L.I. Menshikov, V.V. Sherbina. (1987) and etc.

In the works of the authors Shadrin T.V. (1990), Brazhe T.G. (1990) and others. Investigated self-analysis and improvement of management personnel.

A number of authors present methods of training management personnel - I.G. Abramova. (1985), Rusinova F.M. (1986), Tragunova I.A., Trafimova T.M. (1985) and others.

The structure and content of management functions, the requirements for personal qualities, the motivation of managers, approaches to the assessment and certification of managers are also considered in foreign literature (J. Cretti). and etc.

These areas of research make it possible to determine the content and structure of a sports teacher's activities, on the selection of personnel, on the requirements for the personal characteristics of personnel. Improving the training of highly qualified personnel in the field of physical culture and sports is a task of social importance.

Requirements and the need to search for interrelationships and integral characteristics that construct the activity of a sports teacher into an integral system influenced our choice of an urgent topic, the study of some aspects of the pedagogical skills of a teacher of physical education and sports.

The objectives of the study were: first, the study of the pedagogical culture of physical culture teachers;

secondly, to study the level of pedagogical and managerial competence of sports teachers;

thirdly, to study the degree of professional "burnout" of a physical education teacher.

The study involved coaches in various sports, teachers of the departments of physical education and sports of universities in Uzbekistan. The total age of the subjects ranges from a maximum of 60 years, and a minimum age of 27 years. Work experience - from 5 years or more.

The approach to research from the standpoint of modern science encompasses a set of specific research methods, technical research techniques, and a special methodology for analyzing activities. Justification of the choice of methodological prerequisites for the study, taking into account the integrative nature, is carried out at the junction of pedagogical, psychological science and management theory.

Complex research methods were used in the work:

(method of questioning, polling, observation and analysis, method of mathematical and statistical processing)

The following questionnaires were used: 1- in order to study the pedagogical culture of teachers.

2- to study the level of managerial competence of a sports teacher. "Tests of Professor M.V. Prokhorova 1995 "

3 - study of the degree of professional burnout of physical education teachers. (Vodopyanova N.E.). Questionnaire of professional "Emotional burnout" according to the method of K. Masloch, I.S. Jackson.

Studies of the level of pedagogical culture of physical education teachers were determined according to the proposed ten blocks. With signs including general, moral, communicative, aesthetic, didactic, speech, motor culture, educational activity and work culture.

The results of studies of the level of pedagogical culture of sports specialists are presented in Table 1.

Assessment of the level of indicators of character traits.

Table 1

Indicators of character traits	High level 89.1 points and above	Average 78.7, - 89.0 points	Below average 63.7-78 points	Low level 56.4 points and below.
Σ	10%	45%	45%	5%

The final data (Table 1) show that 10% of teachers have a high level of pedagogical culture. Average and below average characteristic features (45% -5%) are characteristic of the majority of sports teachers

The maximum level of common characteristics of a culture ranges from 70 to 100 points. These are the signs that determine the general and moral culture, which include a civic, humanistic orientation. Development of spiritual interests, adherence to principles, objectivity, conscientiousness, self-criticism, when the reasons for failures and failures must be sought, first of all, in oneself.

A high assessment of the level of motor culture testifies to the ability of a sports teacher to walk correctly, to use gestures optimally, and to choose the right location at educational and training sessions.

Individual components characterizing speech, motor, communicative, didactic, aesthetic, general, moral and culture of thinking were attributed to the average level of pedagogical culture from 78.8 - 89.0 points or 45%.

Indicators of speech, didactic, general, aesthetic, educational culture are from 5 to 20%. This indicates a lack of diction, correctness and purity of speech (without unnecessary words), expressiveness, emotionality of speech.

Sometimes it can be observed that the teacher does not know how to ensure the proper motivation of the athlete, does not possess modern methods and norms of organizing an effective educational process. The aesthetic taste and adherence to the aesthetics of communication, restraint are weakly manifested.

The minimum level of signs of general culture was assessed by 55% of teachers, who noted the components of the culture of thinking, speech, communication, aesthetic signs. Educational activity, indicators of didactic, moral, motor cultures range from 5 to 20%. The

criteria of the culture of thinking show that specialists in the field of physical education and sports have some problems in their ability to foresee possible difficulties and prevent their occurrence. The ability to consider the issue from all sides, taking into account the factors influencing the achievement of the set goal, is not sufficiently expressed. Difficulty applying professional knowledge according to the business need.

The low level of educational activity indicates an insufficient degree of selection of educational methods, taking into account the development of the individual and the team. The ability to involve athletes and students in the process of cooperation, to focus on the process of self-education, to set attractive, meaningful goals is poorly expressed.

Carrying out a study using a specific methodology to study the level of professional competence (TEST prof. MV Prokhorova, 1995) will reveal self-esteem, introspection and expert assessment of the pedagogical competence of a specialist in the field of physical culture and sports.¹

The methodology includes 50 characteristics that are subject to appropriate assessment. Containing components are combined in 10 blocks. This is an intellectual, organizer, business executive, coordinator, educator, innovator, strategist, researcher, diplomat. Using the results of the studies obtained, the basic methods of mathematical and statistical processing were applied (the standard deviation was calculated; the coefficient of variation of the features was determined; the error of the mean value was calculated).

Studies to study the level of managerial competence of sports teachers are presented in table 2.

Criteria for the level of professional competence.

Table 2

Performance rating	Performance indicators
Highest mark from 78 points to 100 points.	Diplomat, educator, coordinator, intellectual, controller, business executive.
Average score from 72 points to 90 points.	Innovator, business executive, diplomat, coordinator, controller.
Low rating of characteristics from 56 points to 86 points.	Researcher, coordinator, strategist, innovator, intellectual, business executive, organizer.

The results of the study of the level of managerial competence in Table 2 indicate that high marks in the range from 78 to 100 points have the characteristics - diplomat, educator, coordinator, intellectual, controller, business executive. These data characterize the professional competence of a sports teacher. The success of the educational activities of specialists of various types was assessed by the method of independent characteristics and has the highest evaluative characteristic. The most pronounced components are self-improvement in the development of skills, self-organization in a sports team. Ability to carry out educational training by means of a specific sports discipline. Instill an interest in moral self-education. Provide a positive social and psychological climate in the sports team.

Similar characteristic data are presented on the average scale. They testify to the ability to see the shortcomings of their work in the course of teaching and educational activities. Analyze and critically evaluate the results of your work. At the same time, the

¹ См.: Прохоровой М.В. Уровень управленческой компетентности спортивного педагога «Тесты профессора М.В. Прохоровой 1995г.»

teacher is able to formulate the tasks of sports and pedagogical activity, to choose effective methods and solutions.

In pedagogical activity, the ability to select capable athletes and complete national teams is of particular importance. The ability to understand the condition of athletes and implement an individually - differentiated approach in the educational and training process. Coordinate your own activities with the activities of colleagues in sports and pedagogical work. High marks emphasize the ability of teachers to establish and maintain friendly relations in the sports team, contacts with colleagues, find a common language with the parents of athletes, with the administration. Be able to defend your opinion. On the same scale, the characteristic indicator "controller" determined the ability of teachers to control the discipline, the course of educational and training and sports processes, maintaining the necessary documents, records of the course of training, competition results, notes. Control the implementation of your own decisions.

In the activities of sports workers, there are economic qualities to create the necessary conditions for the effective organization of the training process in a team. Provide the necessary inventory and equipment, methodological material. To be guided in matters of financing, to be able to make an estimate of the costs of holding sports camps, competitions.

These characteristic qualities are marked on all three scales.

The study of assessments on the third scale, characterizing the teacher as a researcher, strategist, innovator, intellectual, coordinator, organizer, tend to decrease the level of criteria. Also on the optimization and rational organization of their own sports activities. Were revealed low indicators for the ability to develop and introduce new forms and methods of sports and pedagogical work. To be able to generalize the advanced experience of sports achievements and use its innovations in the educational and training process. To be able to adapt ideas, tools and methods used in other sports to the conditions of their own discipline. Analysis of the level of strategic components shows that sports workers find it difficult to plan a sportsman's activities for the long term and to carry out the current planning of educational, training and competitive processes. Poorly expressed or absent the ability to predict competitive results.

Analyzing the data, we come to the conclusion that the indicators - innovator, intellectual, researcher, organizer indicate insufficient and underestimated manifestation of scientific interest in professional activity to the research work of a sports teacher. Analytical work in communication with teachers identified some of the reasons for this attitude. This is a lack of time, inability to use the methodology of research works, or unwillingness to "load" oneself.

The characteristics of the coordinator-organizer indicate the insufficient organizational skills of the teacher in personal professional activities. An operational approach to adjusting educational and training tasks depending on the real situation. Effective coordination and management of joint activities of a sports team is an indicator of a professional approach in the management of professional activities.

The carried out analytical work on approbation of the selected concept of pedagogical competence in the conditions of activity of sports specialists, coaches, the collected materials using the developed methods of diagnostics of the managerial pedagogical competence of specialists made it possible to visually represent the nature of the integration of the above listed characteristics, to determine the typical self-assessment of the pedagogical competence of specialists and to identify shortcomings and gaps in knowledge and skills. The study of pedagogical competence is based on the interaction of a teacher with students of a coach with

athletes of different ages, which is the basis of professional activity. The communicative aspect of pedagogical, managerial, competence requires special attention.

A comprehensive analysis of the pedagogical competence of a specialist implies a combination of various components characterizing the activity made it possible to identify the determining factors. It was revealed that the self-assessment of the level of indicators of pedagogical competence ranges from 32 to 86 points in comparison with the highest mark (90-100 points). Consequently, it is expedient for sports specialists to outline a program, specific guidelines in self-education and self-improvement.

The data must be taken into account in pedagogical activity in order to eliminate shortcomings and for the development of personal characteristics of a sports teacher.

The next stage in the study of the professional activity of a sports teacher is the study of the degree of "professional burnout"

The term "burnout syndrome" of personality to characterize the psychological state of people in the helper professions "from the Latin help".

A new model was developed for the consideration of distress and functional performance. (H.J. Freudenberger "personality burnout syndrome 1974").

Currently, professional burnout syndrome is defined as a state of emotional, mental and physical exhaustion that develops as a result of chronic unresolved stress in the workplace. Its components 1 are emotional exhaustion or feelings of exhaustion and fatigue caused by work. (maximum amount 54 points)

2 scale - depersonalization, presupposes a cynical attitude towards work and the object of one's work (maximum sum of 30 points)

3 scale - reduction of professional achievements i.e. the emergence of a teacher's sense of incompetence in his professional field, about the consciousness of failure in it and failure. (maximum amount 48 points)

The higher the sum of points on each scale separately, the more the examinee has different sides of "burnout". The severity of burnout can be judged by the sum of the points of all scales.

The total sum of indicators on three scales is 132 points. Research conducted among sports teachers has the following data.

Indicators on three scales range from a minimum of 35 points or 26.5%, to 87 points - 65.9%.

The degree of emotional exhaustion is 19.2% (maximum - 54 points). This suggests that discounts bring satisfaction even when you are tired and busy at work.

The level of "depersonalization" (with a maximum of 30 points) is 11% of the number of teachers surveyed.

Data on the third scale - "reduction of personal achievements" The data indicate that the degree of professional performance with all indicators expressing various degrees of "burnout" are in a state of emotional, mental and physical exhaustion, developing in cases of chronic, unresolved stress in the workplace.

Research on the "resilience" of the teacher was determined by four indicators.

1 - resilience, which reveals one's own state and introspection, relationships in various situations.

2 - involvement - shows the position of involvement in one's own attitude to work and to employees.

3 - indicator characterizes self-assessment "control"

4 - introspection characterizing "decision making"

The criterion of indicators of "vitality" of sports teachers

Table-3

Characteristic signs	Maximum indicator	Average indicator	Minimum indicator
Resilience	135-96	76-85	58-71
Involvement	54-45	43-39	24-32
Control	51-42	29-37	19-28
Decision-making	30-26	20-14	3-10

Interpreting the results of studies of self-assessment of resilience (Table 3), we can conclude that teachers feel self-confident, often adopt a democratic style of pedagogical communication and leadership. They can influence the outcome of the situation. They defend their opinions, they are adamant and stubborn.

The state of "involvement" indicates an average degree of satisfaction and enthusiasm for their work.

Control is similar to engagement. That testifies to the specificity of the activity of a physical education teacher, the ability to keep the group under control, to differentiate the load. Be responsible for making decisions and influencing emerging and unexpected problems, depending on the situation and age of work experience.

Self-analysis, characterizing "decision making" (the maximum indicator is 30 and the minimum is 3 points), indicates self-doubt in their own decisions, about indecision to influence what is happening.

It can be assumed that the emerging problems become an obstacle for the teacher in making decisions.

Conclusions

The results of the research revealed significant features characterizing the professional activities of teachers of the departments of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan.

The study of the pedagogical culture of physical education and sports workers showed an insufficient level of general, moral, speech culture of work.

The level of managerial competence testifies to the high self-esteem of teachers in diplomatic, educational, coordination, and intellectual abilities. The lowest self-esteem for organizational, economic, innovative abilities.

These signs of professional activity revealed insufficient, underestimated interest in research, scientific work of sports teachers.

The degree of "professional burnout" indicates that overly emotional people who are not restrained, do not control their feelings more quickly become emotionally exhausted, a feeling of emptiness and fatigue caused by work. The indicator of "introspection" was at a high level, which indicates satisfaction even with fatigue and workload.

References

- Фетискин Н.П., Козлов В.В., Мануйлов Г.М. Социально-психологическая диагностика развития личности и малых групп. - М., 2002. С.360-362
Диагностика профессионального выгорания (К.Маслач, С.Джексон, в адаптации Н.Е.Водопьяновой)
- Никифорова Г.С. Практикум по психологии менеджмента и профессиональной деятельности/под ред. Г.С.Никифорова. МЛО «Адаптивность» (Маклаков, Чермянин)СПб.: Речь, 2001;
- Бордовская Н.В., Ренн А.А. Педагогика учебник нового века. Издательство: Питер, 2006 г. С.277-290
- Прохорова, Марина Валентиновна. Теоретические и методические основы формирования управленческой компетентности специалистов по физической культуре и спорту в условиях высшего физкультурного образования: автореферат дис. доктора педагогических наук: 13.00.04.- Санкт-Петербург, 1993.- 45 с.: ил.

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